

Condition-Based Health Monitoring of Electrical Machines using DWT and LDA Classifier

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Abstract

In the industry, continuous health monitoring of electric motors is considered as, an essential requirement. The continuous operation of the electric motor may cause malfunctions and addressing them timely is a critical challenge. The development of an efficient health monitoring system based on the identification of electrical motor faults is in great demand. This paper addresses the fault detection technique using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) algorithm for continuous health monitoring of electric motor-based systems. The faults have been detected through Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) series procedures using the proposed method. Concurrently, the wavelet transform algorithm produces a frequency-based spectrum related to the stator current parameters to accomplish the fault classification. This study provides an analysis of three motor faults i.e., Phase Imbalance, Rotor Misalignment, and High Contact Resistance (HCR). DWT has the ability to categorize the input signals into an approximate coefficient state for low-frequency signals and a detailed coefficient state for high-frequency signals. In this research, this technique is used to detect faults because it is able of processing signals of very low frequency, and effectively deal with intermittent sharp signals that appear frequently during processing. DWT technique is based on conditional monitoring of an induction motor with precisely detailed coefficients and more skilled at light loads given on a motor shaft with relatively fast execution time compared to Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Furthermore, the comparison of healthy and faulty induction motors has been compiled by the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) technique, a sub-application of MATLAB, and used for faults management purposes. LDA in comparison with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) gives more perfect results. In this research, different faults have been detected with 100% accuracy using the LDA classifier. The implementation of the proposed scheme will be beneficial in avoiding faults by ensuring that preemptive measures are taken timely against these faults, and the production of industries is protected from revenue losses.

Index Terms: Discrete Wavelet Transform, Faults Analysis, Linear Discriminant Analysis Classifier, Motor Current Signature Analysis, Motor Faults.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical machines make up the largest part of all commonly used electrical loads, consuming 30-40% of generated electricity and 70% of the industrial load. Electrical machines are prone to various types of faults [1], and [2]. Today, most of the electrical drives in industries are three-phase induction motors, which are of two distinct types: 1) squirrel cage and 2) wound rotor type. Induction motors have the genetic characteristics of high-value starting torque and are equipped with the feature of precise speed control. The squirrel cage motors have high efficiency and are cheaper than wound rotor types. However, when any fault appears in the induction motors, a major failure occurs in the industry. Detection of faults has remained an exceptional research interest for researchers over the past few decades, thus reducing the cost of maintenance, and preventing unscheduled downtime [3], which results in revenue losses and industry breakdown times. The analysis of faults in the monitoring of the health status of the induction motor is crucial. Here, this study uses the MCSA technique for the prediction of common motor faults that appear in running motors. The

MCSA is the most common [4], reliable [5-7], and efficient technique for diagnosing faults in electrical machines [8-11]. It provides a good understanding of the MCSA. Two sets of data are obtained: one is healthy motor data and the other one is from faults-induced motor data [12], and [13]. The induced faults include Phase Imbalance faults, Rotor Misalignment faults, and High Contact Resistance (HCR) faults. Then by applying signal processing methods features are obtained under transient conditions which are the most critical, and several methods have been proposed to deal with this situation. They are particularly dependent on Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) [14]. In wavelet analysis, coefficients are used to capture signals as fault signatures of the machines, and the wavelet selection is done to get the best results – these research pursuits are the most important. DWT has the ability to categorize the input signals into an approximate coefficient state for low-frequency signals and a detailed coefficient state for high-frequency signals [15]. The wavelet coefficient containing the energy contents is attributed to the fault detection features of induction motors of variable loads. When faults occur, the variance of the DWT coefficients becomes greater compared to that of the healthy state situation [16].

There are many wavelet functions named as, the mother wavelets that help in obtaining the best results not possible by using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The mother wavelet choice is very critical because mother wavelets of different types have different characteristics. Finally, convolutional classification methods are used to classify faults, and fault data signals and healthy data signals are analyzed to find out what type of fault is in the motors.

Figure I: Induction Motor for Experimental Setup

For this research, five identical three-phase induction motors have been taken, and the motor specifications are listed as given in table I.

Table I: Induction Motor Specifications

S. No.	Description	Value
1.	Weight	9.0kg
2.	Power	1.1 kW
3.	RPM	2840
4.	PF	0.84
5.	Temp	40°C
6.	Supply voltage	220 V
7.	Frequency	60Hz

II. FAULT STUDY

In the induction motor, many faults appear and the initial problem identification is quite difficult in this situation [17]. Such faults have many consequences for the health of induction motors, resulting in unbalanced stator currents and voltages, torque fluctuations, reduced efficiency, torque, overheating, and much more than that vibrations. As a result, some currents and the magnitude of the harmonic components of the voltage increase due to these faults. The performance of Induction is affected by the faults. The statistical distribution of these electrical and mechanical faults in induction motors has been proven by surveys undertaken by the IEEE and EPRI [18], and [19]. The statistical studies of the IEEE and EPRI of the motor faults are discussed in [20-24] and listed in table II.

Table II: Study Result

S. No.	By	Bearing (%)	Stator (%)	Rotor (%)	Others (%)
1.	IEEE	42	28	8	22
2.	EPRI	41	36	9	14

III. ROTOR MISALIGNMENT FAULT

From the motor construction, the moving part of the rotor is placed within the casing of the stator and its rotation is along the stator axis. For a healthy motor, the alignment of the rotor is made central within the stator and the axis of rotation needs to be symmetrical and aligned with the geometrical axis of the stators. The result is that it causes a similar air-gap to be between the inner and outer surface of the stator and the rotor. However, if the motor is not centrally aligned and its rotor axis is not identical to the stator geometrical axis, then there remains no air-gap similarity, and the situation is referred to as air-gap eccentricity, deviating from perfect circularity. In fact, in induction motors, the air-gap eccentricity is common to the fault of the rotor, air-gap eccentricity fault will cause an electromagnetic drag which creates unbalanced situations, hence, this way the rotor pullover chance is greater during the starting period when the motor current is the greatest. In severe cases, the stator may be rubbed by the rotor, which may result in damage to the stator or rotor. The eccentricity of air-gap may also cause noise or vibrations and generation of heat [25].

IV. PHASE IMBALANCE FAULT

There exists a stator imbalance due to short-circuit and there is an unbalance in the three-phase system of supply when there is a mismatch between phase or line-to-line voltages of a three-phase system. Three-phase power systems and equipment items are designed to operate with balanced phases as well as line-to-line voltages which are varying typically by a few volts in a three-phase system, but a difference of more than 1% can damage motors and the equipment items. Due to unbalanced voltages, varying currents appear in the motor windings. An unbalanced current results in the current increase in at least one winding such that its temperature increases relative to other windings. Temperature changes reduce the lifetime of the motors and lead to their permanent failure. The fault is transient in nature and so for our research, only two phases are connected when the motor is started and after a second in time, the remaining phase is provided and the motor operates normally.

V. HIGH CONTACT RESISTANCE FAULT

High resistance in the electrical circuit contacts of the induction motor causes localized overheating and causes an unbalance in the voltage supply that results in reduced efficiency and reliability and is subject to fire hazards in the electrical distribution system and in the motors. Therefore, monitoring, high contact resistance faults are important, and correcting the high contact resistance is important for the efficient and safe operation of the industrial facility [26]. A 10-Watt resistor of 1kΩ is used in series with one of the phases.

This paper presents good accuracies of different faults, phase imbalance, high contact resistance faults, and rotor misalignment faults using the LDA Classifier, as tabulated in table III, 100% accuracies are achieved for phase imbalance and high contact resistance faults.

Table III: Fault Types, Accuracy, and Comparison of Results with Accomplishments

S. No.	Reference	Fault Types	Methods	Accuracy
1.	Lasurt et al.	SWF, BRB, Eccentricity Fault	Fuzzy Logic	93% Accuracy
2.	Kolla and Varatharasa	Overloads, Single Phasing, Unbalance Supply Voltage	ANN	-
3.	Proposed Idea	Eccentricity, Phase Imbalance, High Contact Resistance Fault	LDA Classifier	66.67% 100% 100%

VI. DATA ACQUISITION SOFTWARE

LabVIEW 2015 Data Acquisition software or systems engineering application that requires testing, measurement, and control with easy access to hardware for data insights or collection that provides an environment for a graphical programming approach to visualize the functions of the circuit in focus from its application perspective. In this work, it is used for the purpose of data acquisition in industrial automation and controlling tools for various operating systems, particularly those issued for use by Apple, including Microsoft Windows, and, various versions of UNIX and LINUX, and macOS. The motor control front connection is shown in figure II.

Figure II: Experimental Circuit Setup

When the program is running, it first sends a digital signal to the motor ON/OFF circuit and the relay starts the motor. Once the motor is ON the current sensor starts reading the current signature signals for feeding them to the DAQ, which reads the LabVIEW data onto an excel file which is then used offline (or online) for processing the data signals.

Figure III: LabVIEW Front Panel Connection for Motor Controlling

There is also the additional advantage of controlling transients' faults, through a different digital port, and for this purpose, a signal is generated directly after one second which is fed to the aforementioned fault control relay.

VII. DATA FORMATTING AND IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

For the signal processing technique, the study proposed will be executing a sequence of steps as shown by the block diagram in figure IV including wavelet decomposition and feature extraction.

Figure IV: Implementation Procedure

Data obtained from LabVIEW by using DAQ 6009 is fed to MATLAB for offline and for implementing the DWT technique. The sampling frequency is set to 16-kHz for feature extraction and then these features are trained by using LDA Classifier for classifying the state of the health of induction motors under diagnostic test. Data formatting is a crucial factor to get accurate results, that's why data is kept the same in terms of all numbers of samples for healthy and Faulty motor conditions. For this study, data for 12 seconds of time duration is collected which results in about 192000 samples. For each healthy and faulty sample of data in this study, the selected portion of the data will be taken and put into the individual matrices of 1x192000, which means only 192000 data samples array.

VIII. WAVELET DECOMPOSITION

The wavelet transform corresponds to the Fourier Transform with a different merit function, and the major differentiation is that the sine and cosine signals are realized after decomposition by the Fourier Transform. On the other hand, the wavelet transform uses functions translated in both the real domain and the Fourier domain. There is also a mother wavelet which is a prototype for generating other window functions. The mother wavelet is selected based on the similarity between the signal and the mother wavelet. During the analysis of transients in an electrical system, compact support properties-decay towards high frequencies and vanishing moments decay towards low frequencies, have been used to select the best mother wavelet for the analysis. Safavian et al. [27] have concluded that for the detection of electrical systems transients, the wavelet Daubechies (db-4), conflict DWT, and mathematical subfield of numerical analysis, B-spline are equally suitable. Typically, visual inspection shape matching is applied to capture the most accurate mother wavelet.

Figure V: Mother Wavelets

Figure VI: Implementation of db-4 Decomposition for Motor Signal during Healthy Condition

Figure VII: Implementation of db-4 Decomposition for Motor Signal during Phase Imbalance Fault Condition

Figure VIII: Implementation of db-4 Decomposition for Motor Signal during Rotor Misalignment Fault Condition

Figure IX: Implementation of db-4 Decomposition for Motor Signal during High Contact Resistance Fault Condition

Here in this research current signals, which are spike patterns, and hence this study uses Daubechies-4 wavelet also wavelet level 9 is used for $F_s = 16$ kHz. Since the signal contains a natural component of noise at every 50 multiples, hence levels other than 6, 7, 8, and 9 levels are not considered. Moreover, figure VI, figure VII, figure VIII, and figure IX show healthy motor and fault-induced motor signals with their wavelet decomposition at detailed coefficient levels. It is concluded that when the fault appears, then the differences in the DWT coefficients become higher compared to the Healthy Motor condition. Faults include Phase Imbalance, Rotor Misalignment, and High Contact Resistance faults. The current signature values after feature extraction are then fed to the classifier for the classification of faults. Furthermore, figure V

represents different mother wavelets for comparison and the selection of similarity between the signals being processed.

IX. FEATURE EXTRACTION

For the classification of our data, Wavelet Entropy is used which is a measure of extraction of information from an arbitrary nature of uncertain events. Information with a broad, flat probability distribution will have a higher entropy unlike information having narrow peak distribution. Hence, improbable events will produce more information than possible events, and wavelet entropy in time is calculated as shown in eq. (1):

$$E(s) = \sum E(S_i) \tag{1}$$

There are also other ways of calculating the results using the Mean and RMS and computing standard deviations. But in our research, there is mainly focus on Mean, Entropy, and RMS value.

X. CLASSIFICATION

Based on the above features, data will be classified, note here that 50% of the data will be utilized for training purposes and 50% of the data will be used to test the classifier, and here LDA is used as a classification technique. The Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) is a method of finding a linear combination of features, it best separates two or more examples of classes and the result obtained as the linear classifier [28-30]. LDA, $j(w)$ is simply a measure of the difference between class averages normalized by a scale within a class scattering matrix, hence can be mathematically represented as eq. (2) and shown in figure X. The class_0, class_1, and class_2 are representing here, the Phase Imbalance fault samples, High Contact Resistance fault samples, and Rotor Misalignment fault samples. After LDA implementation, the figure given shows, how the faults are properly classified, which means each sample is managed in its own category of fault and nature of the fault.

$$J(w) = \frac{|\bar{\mu}_1 - \bar{\mu}_2|^2}{s_1^2 - s_2^2} = \frac{w^T S_B w}{w^T S_w w} \tag{2}$$

Figure X: Linear Discriminant Analysis

XI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results that this study has achieved after classification are already very promising, and the judging criteria are 'Accuracy' which is defined as a sample classified out of the total number of samples and can be written as:

$$ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} * 100 \tag{3}$$

Where:

- TP = True Positive
- TN = True Negative
- FP = False Positive and
- FN = False Negative.

All the results are listed below in table IV. When fault appears, the variation in frequency components, first and second order harmonics is observed larger with respect to the healthy condition of the motor, as shown in the figures i.e., figure VI, figure VII, figure VIII, and figure IX.

Table IV: Fault Types Accuracy and Features Characteristics Accuracy and Features Characteristics

Fault	Characteristic Features	% Accuracy		
		Level 7	Level 8	Level 9
Rotor Misalignment	Entropy	83.3	83.3	66.67
	Mean	83.3	66.67	66.67
	RMS	50	66.67	66.67
Phase Imbalance	Entropy	100	100	100
	Mean	100	100	100
	RMS	100	100	66.67
High Contact Resistance	Entropy	100	100	100
	Mean	100	100	100
	RMS	100	100	83.3

XII. CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results as shown in table IV, different faults of a motor have been reported. The faults such as Rotor Misalignment, Phase Imbalance, and High Contact Resistance have been detected using the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classification technique with good accuracy. Further, in this paper for rapid detection of the stated faults characteristic features like Entropy, RMS and Means have been extracted using Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT) algorithm. Moreover, the detailed coefficient graphs of healthy and faulty motors under different conditions have been discussed. The state condition of motors as shown in the results, the variance of the DWT coefficients gets higher amplitude compared to the healthy motor. The research finds that different faults have been detected with 100% accuracy using the LDA classifier. The particular levels of accuracy are considered, as the optimum choice for induction motor-based health monitoring systems. Hence this technique can be used as more valuable for the prediction of the state of the health of Induction Motors (IMs).

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Authors Contributions

Each author has equally contributed to achieving the objectives of this research study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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